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Characterization and Modeling of Woven SiC_f/SiC_m Tubular Composites

Prof. Ghatu Subhash
Prof. Bhavani Sankar
Prof. Raphael Haftka

Mr. Hemanth T. Nagaraju
Mr. James Nance

Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering
University of Florida, Gainesville, FL USA

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Motivation and Applications

- Nuclear-grade continuous $\text{SiC}_f/\text{SiC}_m$ composites have high resistance to radiation-damage and good damage tolerance in extreme radiation environments.
- They have high thermal resistance, low thermal-expansion coefficient, and high modulus and strength
- Candidate materials for nuclear components for fusion and fission reactors
- Their excellent chemical compatibility with coolant and fuel systems in high temperature gas cooled fast reactors makes them ideal candidates for cladding materials for energy multiplier modules, channel boxes in light water reactors (LWR) and in-vessel components

Objectives

- Quantify various heterogeneities in the microstructure of the SiC/SiC composite tubes
- Determine the uncertainty in mechanical properties and strength as a function of variability in microstructural features
- Develop **constitutive relations** and **failure envelopes** for 2D woven composite tubes using the **direct micromechanics method** and establish **multiaxial failure criteria** for generalized complex loading conditions

Manufacturing Method

- SiC fibers of 10-micron diameter are coated with 20-500 nm thick pyrolytic carbon (PyC) or boron nitride.
- Fibers are bundled into yarns and woven in plain-weave configuration at $0/\pm 30^\circ$ stacking over a mandrel into tubular geometry
- Chemical vapor infiltration is used to deposit SiC as the matrix phase.

Imperfections in SiC_f/SiC composites

Layup thickness

Fiber bundle density and porosity

Matrix thickness

Parameters of Interest

Variations in Microstructure and Geometric Parameters

- Fiber diameter distribution
- Tow cross-section dimensions
- Interphase thickness
- Porosity distribution
- Tow angle variations
- Tow fiber volume fraction
- Tube Inner diameter/outer diameter
- Wall thickness

X-ray computed tomography (XCT)

Variations in Mechanical Properties and Strength

- Compression
 - Axial and radial direction
 - Static and dynamic strain rate
- Flexure
 - Static and dynamic strain rate
- Indent
 - Static/dynamic
- Hoop

Fiber Diameter Distribution via XCT

Porosity Distribution

Porosity:
14.3%

Wall Thickness

Challenges in Modeling Failure Behavior of Curved Woven Composites

Unlike unidirectional composites (UC) the failure theory for woven composites (WC) is not well developed. The challenges in modeling WC are:

1. UC use laminate theory (each layer is assumed to be homogenous orthotropic material) and hence the unit-cell at macroscale is in a state of uniform stress. The unit cell in WC is much larger (1-2 mm in width) and even simple loading can impart complex stress state, stress gradient and non-uniform elastic constants.
2. Most UC have softer and compliant polymer matrix. The SiC_f/SiC composites have both fiber and matrix phases of similar constitution and properties. The CVI process introduces vast number of defects and microstructural heterogeneities. The inherent brittleness and heterogeneity, renders their failure behavior vastly different from UC.
3. Although significant progress has been made in understanding failure behavior of WC in planar configuration, the **failure behavior of curved and tubular geometry** is not studied theoretically.

Approach: Path to FE Mesh of Curved RVE

$$\theta = \frac{x - x_{mid}}{R}, r = R + z$$

$$x' = r * \sin(\theta)$$

$$z' = r * \cos(\theta)$$

Transform the vectors used to define Material Coordinate system of yarn

$$V' = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & 0 & \sin(\theta) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin(\theta) & 0 & \cos(\theta) \end{bmatrix} * V$$

Comparison of Responses between Curved vs. Flat Geometries

Curved RVE: Apply Pressure
(plane strain)

Volume Averaged Hoop
Strain

Apply the volume averaged hoop
strain to flat RVE

Obtain the Stresses in Yarn and
matrix of Flat RVE

For credible comparison maintain same fiber volume fractions in two RVEs:

Fiber Volume fraction within a yarn (V_{yf}) = Volume of Fiber/ Volume of yarn

Yarn Volume fraction (V_y) = Volume of yarn / Volume of RVE

Volume fraction of RVE = $V_{yf} \times V_y$

Comparison of curved and flat RVEs for 2D biaxial 30° braided composites

For Yarn	Curved RVE		Flat RVE		Deviation	
(Transversely Isotropic)	Max (MPa)	Min (MPa)	Max (MPa)	Min (MPa)	For Max (%)	For Min (%)
σ_1	437.61	33.31	273.51	77.73	-37.5	133.34
σ_{23_p1}	892.02	232.19	798.17	356.16	-10.52	53.39
σ_{23_p2}	118.14	-154.41	144.62	-105	22.41	-32
τ_{23}	442.82	156.86	387.15	144.71	-12.57	-7.74
$T = \sqrt{\tau_{12}^2 + \tau_{13}^2}$	274.23	51.82	197.55	53.07	-27.96	2.41

For Matrix	Curved RVE	Flat RVE	Deviation (%)
Maximum principal Stress (MPa)	1764.3	1399.5	-20.68
Minimum principal Stress (MPa)	-361	-101	-72.11

Direct Micromechanics Method (DMM)

Determination of microstress distribution and constitutive relationship in RVE

$$\begin{Bmatrix} [N] \\ [M] \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [A] & [B] \\ [B] & [D] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} [\varepsilon] \\ [k] \end{Bmatrix}$$

Determine microstress for applied force and moment resultant

$$\{\sigma^e\} = [F^e] \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon^M \\ k^M \end{Bmatrix}$$

Evaluate macro-level force and moment resultants

$$N_{ij} = \left(\frac{1}{ab}\right) \sum \sigma_{ij}^e V^e$$

and

$$M_{ij} = \left(\frac{1}{ab}\right) \sum z \sigma_{ij}^e V^e$$

Determination of Failure Envelopes

Future Work

- Establish design criterion of failure of composite tube
- Incorporate uncertainty quantification into failure envelopes
- Validate with experimental data
- Mechanical testing and evaluation of strength variations as a function of microstructural variability